

Correlation coefficients were 0.456**, 0.399**, and 0.527**.

Average cold tolerance of varieties was calculated for several growth stages: $S = s_1 + s_2 + s_3 + \dots s_n/n$. There was a highly significant correlation between

average score and elevation (see figure). Japonicas tend to have cold tolerance above 1,500 m elevation, indicas below 1,000 m, and japonica/indica between 1,000 and 1,500 m.

Agronomic characteristics also change with elevation. Lemma, palea, and apiculus colors are more intense and flag leaves shorter with increasing elevation. *ℒ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DEEP WATER

Selecting deep water rices with ratooning ability

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Cropping intensity in deep water rice areas is low because long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive varieties are needed. Boro or winter rice often is harvested too late to allow proper establishment of deep water rice. Photoperiod-sensitive rices with good ratooning ability, submergence tolerance, and elongation ability have potential as a dry season crop and as a deep water ratoon.

We evaluated 118 entries for ratooning ability in an unreplicated trial in Nov 1982-May 1983 at IRRI (see figure). At maturity, plants were cut to 15-cm height and 15 d later were scored for ratooning ability. Of the selections, 109 were evaluated in 1983 wet season and 1983-84 dry season to confirm their performance and ascertain the photoperiod sensitivity of the ratoons.

In the Nov 1982 planting, main crop flowering, maturity, and height varied substantially, perhaps because they were first planted at IRRI in dry season and have not been selected for uniformity. Within a variety, many hills did not produce ratoon tillers. Several plants, however, had good ratooning ability, which was based on high tiller number (≥ 16), at least 3 leaves per tiller before flowering, and freedom from virus diseases. Some entries flowered immediately after ratooning, others remained vegetative, and a few showed segregation for flowering. We selected entries that flowered soon after

Selection of deep water rices with ratooning ability, IRRI, 1982-84

ratooning and those that flowered late.

Early flowering ratoons were evaluated in Jun-Dec 1983. The main crop lodged seriously, and the ratoon crop had generally poor regeneration (0-

10%). Only Raj Bhawalia (Acc. 26517A) had relatively high regeneration. We attributed the poor ratooning to lodging during early growth.

Ratoons with delayed flowering were

Characteristics of outstanding selections in main and ratoon crops, IRRI, 1983-84 dry season.

Selection	Accession no., parentage	Main crop							Ratoon crop			
		Days to flowering	Ht (cm)	Panicles/ plant	Yield/ plant (g)	Lodging score	Cold tolerance score ^a	Elonga- tion	Regen- eration	Ratoon rating	Tillers/ plant	Flowering ^b
Gowai 50-9	Acc. 6493 A	104	141	15	18	3	9	1	93	1	17	+
Gowai 476	Acc. 6501 A	126	163	15	20	9	5	1	80	1	24	-
Cholamon 658	Acc. 6517 A	133	177	19	21	7	5	1	85	1	20	-
Lalamon 245	Acc. 6558 A	125	155	14	15	9	5	1	99	1	30	+/-
Kalamon 243	Acc. 6599 A	125	165	14	11	7	7	1	96	1	26	-
Karkati 87	Acc. 6618 A	117	152	21	15	9	5	1	97	1	35	-
Raj Bhawalia	Acc. 26517 A	98	156	15	9	7	5	1	98	1	18	+
Sechi Amon	Acc. 26522 A	111	170	18	13	9	5	1	82	1	23	-
BKNR76014-1-9-2		104	171	11	29	5	9	7	84	1	19	-
CN691-3		120	117	20	32	0	7	7	95	1	24	-
CN658-R-R-R	Jaladhi 2/CR1005	125	140	22	16	3	3	7	97	1	27	-
CN658-R-R-R	Jaladhi 2/CR1005	111	125	11	20	3	7	7	83	1	23	-
CN665-R	Pankalash/OC1393	125	156	10	15	5	5	7	83	1	24	-

^aAt seedling stage. ^b+ = flowered, - = flowering, +/- = segregating.

evaluated in 1983-84 dry season (Nov-May). Some entries were common in both seasons. Most selections ratooned well, but the extent of regeneration and crop vigor varied widely. Thirteen selections were made from 12 entries based on consistent performance for at least 2 seasons (see table). Regeneration

was 80-99%. A few entries compensated for relatively low regeneration by producing more tillers per hill. There were 17-35 ratoon tillers per plant. Of the 13 selections, 10 did not flower, 2 flowered, and 1 segregated for flowering.

Although some entries ratooned well in both seasons, the different dry season

and wet season responses of many selections suggest the important influence of environmental factors on ratooning ability. Although early lodging reduced ratooning, lodging in late reproductive phase (1983-84 dry season) did not seem to influence ratooning ability. *ℳ*

Evaluation of the 9th International Rice Deep Water Observational Nursery (IRDWON) in waterlogged coastal soils

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The IRDWON comprised 124 entries and local check Kalamota (Sel). Seeds were sown 26 Jun 1984 and transplanted on 24 Jul in unreplicated plots. Entries

each were transplanted in 5.0- × 0.75-m plots at 25-cm spacing. Water depth was 39.4±1.45 cm in Aug, 3 1.6±1.8 cm in Sep, 20.8±1.2 cm in Oct, and 20.0 cm in Nov.

Grain yield, plant survival percentage, flowering duration, plant height, and panicles per plant were recorded from five randomly selected plants from each entry. IR21567-9-2-2-2-1-3 yielded highest and 5% more than the local check (see table). Leb Mue Nahng 111

and RD19 yielded 0.04 and 0.98 t/ha. IR21567-9-2-2-2-1-3 and NC493 will be evaluated in local yield trials. *ℳ*

Deep water rice yield trials on the Cuu Long Delta

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We compared 11 popular varieties and 2 promising lines in a yield trial for deep water rice at CLRRI in 1984 monsoon season (see table). Twenty square meter plots were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Rice was transplanted at 30 × 30 cm spacing, and received 30-30-0 kg NPK/ha. Maximum water depth was 95 cm on 12-15 Nov.

The lines had good plant type, but did not yield well because of photoperiod insensitivity and high sterility. Trang Chum, Radine China 4, and Chum

Performance of some promising rice entries in the 9th IRDWON, Canning, India.

Entry	Plant height (cm)	Panicles, plant (no.)	Plant survival (%)	Days to flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR21567-9-2-2-2-1-3	124	9	92	113	5.5
NC493	184	10	100	129	5.1
BR222-B-358	151	11	97	126	4.7
B4259-48-1-3-1-3	118	7	95	133	4.5
IR331339-6-1-6	124	14	87	125	4.5
<i>Checks</i>					
Leb Mue Nahng III	169	6	75	137	0.0
RD19	107	14	18	149	0.0
Kalamota (Sel.)	166	9	100	131	5.2